

DARKERSKY4CE: Implementing Transnational Pilot Actions for Light Pollution Mitigation in Central Europe

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Abstract: Artificial light at night (ALAN) is recognized as an environmental stressor impairing biodiversity, human health and astronomical observations. Central Europe ranks among the most light-polluted regions globally, making coordinated, cross-border action a pressing need. The Interreg Central Europe project DARKERSKY4CE (2024–2027) brings together partners from Italy, Poland, Hungary, Germany, Austria, and Slovenia to promote understanding of light pollution and to integrate scientific, policy and social perspectives into actionable strategies. Rather than framing ALAN only as an environmental problem, the project approaches darkness as a shared resource — supporting biodiversity, cultural identity, and tourism potential. Four Pilot Actions (PA) will be implemented across five Pilot Demonstration Sites (PDS), testing complementary strategies to reduce light pollution and strengthen local engagement. In Germany, municipalities will replace and reprogram public street lamps to evaluate lighting technologies. In Poland, an educational astro-tourism offer will be developed through a dark sky route, night-time observations and workshops for students and adults. In Italy, participatory dialogues will explore how to prevent different lighting interests from becoming a source of conflict. In Hungary and Austria, partners will jointly monitor ecological responses using light sensors, acoustic recorders and eDNA tools, testing innovative and transferable monitoring protocols. DARKERSKY4CE is currently at the stage of developing a shared framework for implementation, indicators, and stakeholder engagement. The presentation will introduce the project's objectives, planned pilot activities, and expected outcomes, highlighting how transnational collaboration can contribute to a broader vision for sustainable nightscapes and the future creation of a Dark Sky Macro-Region in Central Europe.

Keywords: transnational; cooperation; policy; piloting; solutions.

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